

Supplementary Information (SI1) to the paper:

Soil organic carbon models need independent time-series validation for reliable prediction

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This SI describes the methodological procedure applied to carry out the systematic review of the literature (Notes 1), provides additional figures to the main manuscript and qualitative description of the literature analysis (Notes 2) as well as a summary of the results of the systematic review (Notes 3).

Supplementary Notes 1: Method to the literature analysis

The literature review consisted in four chronological steps: (i) literature screening, (ii) literature selection, (iii) literature systematic analysis, and (iv) refinement of literature selection (Fig. S1). We provide here a detailed presentation of the procedure followed to allow reproducibility of the review process^{1,2}.

Fig. S1. Procedure implemented to carry out the literature review and its systematic analysis.

We used two complementary methods to conduct a survey of the literature (i) on SOC model developments and applications: first, an expert elicitation allowed us to gather relevant literature, and second, a systematic investigation using Google Scholar helped complement the literature screening. The expert elicitation first started on October 2021 with the organisation of a scientific workshop on “Diversity and complementarity in SOC modelling approaches” at the *École Normale Supérieure de Paris* (<https://cland.lsce.ipsl.fr/events/2021/soil-organic-carbon>). The workshop brought together an international panel of senior and early-career scientists, including 28 invited experts, who are also co-authors of the present publication, and up to 50 remote participants. Experts were invited based on their track record on SOC model development and application, as well as considering a balance in the ratio of gender, age and nationality, although due to pandemic restrictions, European and particularly French researchers were over-represented. Expert involvement in the literature search process depended on two publication time periods. For the 1930-2009 period, the database already compiled by Manzoni and Porparato (2009)³ was taken as a landmark reference of the SOC model review up to 2009, extensible to the assessment of SOC model scopes and validations. This represented 205 peer-reviewed articles and 246 individual models in the 1930-2009 period. For the 2010-2021 period, a first literature search was made by asking each expert to send all relevant peer-reviewed articles they knew on SOC model new developments and/or validations. This expert elicitation method of literature search was then complemented by a further literature review in Google Scholar using the key words: ‘soil’ AND ‘carbon’ AND ‘model*’ for the 2009-2021 period. The literature

search led to the inclusion of 167 publications potentially relevant to our review for the 2010-2021 period and, overall, to the screening of 413 publications over the period 1930-2021.

In screening step (ii), models focusing on SOC were identified. For the 1930-2009 period, the publications gathered by Manzoni and Porporato (2009)³ included both SOC and soil organic nitrogen (SON) models and considered eight distinct contexts (thereafter ‘level’) in which models were applied: fine scale models (biocrust, rhizosphere, aggregate, microbial community models), litter, soil, ecosystem (i.e., vegetation and soil), and global (including several ecosystems or coupling with climatic conditions). Given our goal to assess model validation for SOC prediction, models describing only nitrogen dynamics were removed. We considered only models developed at soil, ecosystem and global levels, as well as microbial community models applicable to whole-soil contexts. Models specifically developed at biocrust, rhizosphere, aggregate and litter levels were removed. In addition, statistical approaches based on empirical coefficients following tier 1 or tier 2 approaches as defined by the IPCC⁴ as well as models based on other statistical approaches such as random forest tree analysis or Bayesian approach^{5,6} were excluded so that we focused only on process-based SOC models corresponding to tier 3 approaches. Applying all these criteria led to discard 119 and 46 of the screened publications for the 1930-2009 and 2010-2021 periods respectively. Overall, a total of 248 publications, including 236 original SOC models plus 117 models with new development e.g. Wutzler and Reichstein (2013)⁷ or new validations e.g. Pansu et al. (2007)⁸ of an already published model, were selected at this stage.

To address the scientific questions raised in the introduction, in step (iii) we systematically examined: model features, scope, and validation procedures. To that end, we established and filled a database providing a quantitative assessment of the full characteristics of each model from each publication (see appendix A and supplementary data 1):

- Model features. Following Manzoni and Porporato (2009)³, we systematically investigated the following features of SOC models: level (see model levels above); temporal scale of interest from hour to decade; spatial scale of interest from microscopic to regional; microbial decomposition, distinguishing linear and nonlinear kinetics with regards to SOC stocks and; control of abiotic factors on SOC decay, including no effect, rate modifier control and physiological effect on microbial decomposers.
- Model scope. We distinguished three objectives: hypothesis-testing and/or formalization, diagnosis of a dataset and functional prediction. Those categories are not exclusive, which means that a given model can fall into more than one of these categories. Models falling into the scope of hypothesis testing can aim to understanding the effect of one or more biogeochemical or microbial processes on the model behaviour e.g. Thornley (2001)⁹ and/or for developing a hypothetical-deductive approach to answer a scientific question e.g. Stewart et al. (2007)¹⁰ and/or for providing a mathematical or schematic representation of mechanisms governing SOC dynamic e.g. Daufresne, T. & Loreau (2001)¹¹, Moore et al. (2004)¹². These can be purely theoretical models not based on empirical data or based on calibrated models using empirical data to test hypotheses. Diagnostic models are used to get information from a dataset such as estimates of microbial traits from time series data e.g. Yan et al. (2016)¹³. Finally, predictive models aim to accurately simulate past or future SOC dynamics under different land-use or climatic scenarios Clivot et al. (2019)¹⁴, Huang et al. (2021)¹⁵, Parton et al. (1994)¹⁶. This scope is the one for which model validation is the most critical for reliable projections and prescriptions.
- Model validation. We characterised validation through seven types of meta-data: first is there a validation against observation data (yes/no)? Second, are the validation procedures based on data independent from those used for model calibration (yes/no)? Third, how is

the validation performed with regard to temporal SOC dynamics: is it a one point in time, space-for-time or diachronic validation based on time-series observations? Fourth, what are validation conditions: laboratory (e.g., incubation experiment), field (e.g., long-term experiment), SOC network (e.g., LUCAS topsoil survey¹⁷) and/or reconstructed datasets (e.g., scaling up observation values of respiration fluxes from field measurements to construct global gridded datasets of soil heterotrophic respiration)¹⁸? Fifth, what is the type of data used for the validation: total SOC stocks/contents and/or mineralization (CO₂) fluxes and/or microbial C stocks/contents? Sixth, how is goodness evaluated: based on graphical and/or statistical test validation? Seventh, what are the pedoclimatic and geographic contexts of model validation? These meta-data provide a clear picture of model validation procedures and thus allow a quantitative analysis of how models are evaluated in relation to their features and scope.

To avoid the over-representation of certain model scopes and validation procedures when several model variants were presented in a single publication, in step (iv) we limited the number of models to one per publication. This approach led to arbitrarily selecting certain model variants and discarding others when publications compared genuinely different models e.g. Wieder et al. (2018)¹⁹. Therefore, in order to avoid both biases associated with over-representation of model scope and validation, and arbitrary selection of model features, the following refinement criteria were applied: in publications dealing with several SOC models, only those models with exactly the same features were discarded from the review analysis. This refinement of criteria reduces the number of models systematically reviewed to 220 original SOC models plus 56 previously published models with new developments or validations. In other words, the second filter applied in step (iv) did not consist in discarding publications but in discarding within each publication those models which had the same features.

Model features, scope, and validation approaches are regarded here as primary data, which are visualized as time series (Fig. 2), and analysed via spider diagrams (Fig. 3) and prevalence of validation procedure (Table 1). Because fewer than 20 models were retained before the 1980's, models published before 1979 are grouped into one temporal category, while the few models published after 2020 are grouped with models published in the 2010's decade. This grouping resulted in five-time intervals (<1980, 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, >2010) that were used to illustrate temporal changes in model properties in order to answer the scientific question (i).

To assess recent trends in SOC model validation, we draw two spider diagrams depicting the relative distributions of model features and scopes depending on the type of validation performed. This accounted for 189 models in 177 publications since 2000. In addition, we carried out an analysis of validation types for models aiming at prediction since 2000 by considering two relevant axes: (i) types and (ii) conditions of model validation. This represented 92 models in 45 publications. These analyses served to answer the scientific question (ii).

This quantitative review of the literature was complemented by a qualitative analysis of the history of model validation for some specific cases of both first-order and non-linear SOC models. This analysis aimed to highlight pathways that model validations can take and link them to the history of the different models.

Supplementary Notes 2: Additional figures and analysis of various pathways of model validations in relation to their development

Fig. S2. Spider diagram of model features and scopes since 2000 – accounting for 189 models in 177 publications –, distinguishing between models validated by independent diachronic validation (blue) and models evaluated in other ways (red). Values on the axes of the diagram indicate the percentage of models validated in each case. => Soil level and >= Ecosystem level indicates models at the soil level or below and models at the ecosystem level or above respectively.

Table S1. How is validation performed when models aim at predicting: cluster analysis of type of validation depending on conditions of validations with SOC models reviewed since 1933. Values indicate number of models.

Since 1933	Independent diachronic	Other type of validation	No validation
Against laboratory experiments	6	18	x
Against field experiment	14	50	x
Against network measurements	1	8	x
Against reconstructed dataset	4	15	x
No validation	x	x	6

How are different models evaluated when they aim at predicting SOC dynamics? To answer this question, we analysed the validation pathway of three first-order kinetic models: Century, AMG and the Q-model (Box 1) and two non-linear kinetic models: MIMICS and Millennial (Box 2). We choose these five models as they represent complementary modelling approaches: Century is the most cited SOC model²⁰; AMG is a simple model designed for cropland in temperate zone with high predictive performance; Q-model has the particularity of representing a continuum of SOC decomposition rates (equivalent to having a continuous distribution of SOC pools); MIMICS is now one of the most widely used microbial soil models, applied from site to global scales; last, Millennial aims at becoming the new generation of SOC models by considering both non-linear kinetics and describing measurable SOC compartments. This

qualitative review is summarized in Fig. S1 retracing the validation pathways of these five models along two crucial categories: (i) independent *versus* non-independent and (ii) diachronic *versus* non-diachronic model validation.

Fig. S3. Validation pathways of five selected models including Century ●, AMG *, Q-model ■, MIMICS ◆, and Millennial ×. Validation pathways of first-order and non-linear kinetic and models are represented respectively in solid and dashed lines. The triangle symbols ► indicates the time direction. Some models have been used as starting point for others. In this case, for simplicity, we represented them as a continuous line even though it can be seen as a new branch.

Box S1: Development and validation of first-order kinetic models

The Century model (Fig. S2a) was developed in 1987 to simulate long-term C and N dynamics at a yearly time step²¹. The model splits organic matter into different conceptual pools defined according to their average residence time. The C and N sub-models were originally evaluated against steady-state soil C and N stocks from independent observations of 24 grassland sites, but without evaluating the model's ability to reproduce temporal dynamics. Century was later developed to include P and S dynamics²², and was evaluated against long-term (i.e., ~100 years) data from agricultural sites. A further improvement to the model was published in 1992 (Century v3) to account for the effect of agricultural practices on SOC dynamics and was originally evaluated using one point in time data from 11 partly independent grassland sites²³. Century v4 was released to deal with a wide range of cropping system²⁴, including new parametrizations, but without presenting new validations. However, later publications provided independent diachronic validation of the model^{16,25-27}. Century has been integrated as the soil module of the DGVM ORCHIDEE, where it was initially evaluated against independent average estimates of global SOC stocks²⁸. Since then, the CENTURY module within ORCHIDEE has been evaluated based on independent dataset from field experiments as well as global dataset^{29,30}.

The AMG model (Fig. S2b) was first published by Andriulo et al., (1999)³¹ to simulate decadal scale changes in cropland SOC. The model simulates SOC dynamics at an annual time step, by considering two SOC compartments – an active and an inert pool initialized from a known initial SOC stock and default ratio of these two pools. Originally the model validation did not involve independent data. A new version simulating the effects of straw residue export on SOC in croplands was developed and validated³². More recent versions (AMGv2) account for abiotic factor effects on decay constants¹⁴. AMGv2 was evaluated against extensive topsoil SOC data from long-term fields agricultural experiments in France by applying a leave-one-site-out cross-validation approach. An additional diachronic independent validation was performed in the context of a model intercomparison³³. A modified version of AMG (v3) incorporating priming effects was developed to simulate the evolution of SOC stocks in a 47-year tillage experiment, but without independent validation. Thanks to its simplicity and to a new initialization method based on measurement of the stable SOC pool, AMGv2 allows robust predictions of SOC dynamics under varying pedo-climatic and agricultural conditions, with a generic set of model parameters³⁴.

The continuous quality model (Q-model) (Fig. S2c) is based on the idea originally developed by Carpenter³⁵ that organic matter cannot be separated into discrete compartments but it can be characterized by a continuous distribution of decay constants³⁶. In the Q-model, the initial distribution of decay rates results in a time-dependent distribution of C contents shifting along the decay rate axis. In turn, integrating this C distribution over the whole range of decay constants yields the total organic matter C and how it varies through time. Microbial biomass is modelled implicitly. The Q-model has been used for prediction of C stocks in equilibrium conditions after validation against SOC at national scale in Sweden, but using only one point in time and sites partly overlapping those used for calibration in previous publication³⁷. The continuous quality concept has gained traction in recent years, with more process-based models building on similar ideas, although without validation against observation data to date³⁸.

a CENTURY

	Non-diachronic evaluation	Diachronic evaluation
independent evaluation	Ability to predict spatial variability	Ability to predict spatio-temporal dynamics
Non independent evaluation	Conceptualization	Calibration

Validation timeline for CENTURY model:

- Century v1 (1987) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- Century v3 (1992) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- Orchidea (2005) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- Century v2 (1988) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- Orchidea (2015-2018) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- Century v4 (1993-2004) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- Century v4 (1993) - Diachronic non-independent evaluation

b AMG

	Non-diachronic evaluation	Diachronic evaluation
independent evaluation	Ability to predict spatial variability	Ability to predict spatio-temporal dynamics
Non independent evaluation	Conceptualization	Calibration

Validation timeline for AMG model:

- AMGv0 (1999) - Diachronic non-independent evaluation
- AMGv1 (2008) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- AMGv2 (2019) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- AMGv2 (2021) - Diachronic independent evaluation
- AMGv3 (2020) - Diachronic independent evaluation

c Q-MODEL

	Non-diachronic evaluation	Diachronic evaluation
independent evaluation	Ability to predict spatial variability	Ability to predict spatio-temporal dynamics
Non independent evaluation	Conceptualization	Calibration

Validation timeline for Q-MODEL:

- Theoretical continuous model (1981) - Non-diachronic non-independent evaluation
- Q-Model (1985) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- Q-Model (2016) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- C-Stability Model (2021) - Non-diachronic independent evaluation
- 6 - Diachronic independent evaluation

Fig. S4. Schematic representation of the (a) Century model, (b) AMG model and (c) Q-model and their validation pathways. Rectangles stand for processes, arrows stand for carbon fluxes, round stand for C pools.

Box S2: Development and validation of non-linear kinetic models

The MIMICS model (Fig. S3a) was developed first as a soil decomposition model based on non-linear Michaelis-Menten kinetics with dependence on both temperature and clay content, and two microbial groups – fast-growing copiotrophs and slow-growing oligotrophs³⁹. MIMICS was initially evaluated using independent measurements of a long-term litter decomposition study across multiple sites and of SOC stock changes in two long-term warming experiments. In Wieder et al., (2015)⁴⁰, an ‘available SOM’ pool was added, which microbes could access together with the litter pools (while chemically or physically protected pools are unavailable to microbes). This new version of MIMICS was evaluated using long-term independent measurements of litter decomposition, SOM stock and response of litter and SOM components to nitrogen fertilization. Coupled N cycling was added to MIMICS in Kyker-Snowman et al., (2020)⁴¹ and independently evaluated for litter C and N loss against observations from multiple sites participating in the 10-year Long-Term Inter-site Decomposition Experiment Team (LIDET). MIMICS has also been incorporated into a biogeochemical testbed and compared with other models^{42–45}. At the global scale, MIMICS did not outperform a simpler first-order kinetic model (CASA C-N-P) in a diachronic validation against heterotrophic respiration from independent reconstructed datasets⁴², although the MIMICS models generated additional insight that are not afforded by simpler models.

The Millennial model (Fig. S3b) contains five pools related to measurable properties and processes. The initial description of the model and comparison to the Century model was published in Abramoff et al., (2018)⁴⁶. The updated Millennial Version 2 (V2)⁴⁷ was evaluated at steady state against a global-scale spatial dataset of SOC stocks and fractions (mineral-associated organic matter (MAOM) and non-MAOM, separated at a cut-off value of 50-60 μm). The model fitted 15 out of 24 parameters selected using sensitivity analysis. These parameters were fitted to the data using a cross-validation procedure which trained the model on 80% of the data and held out 20% of the data for validation. The Millennial V2 model outperformed the Century model in predicting soil C stocks across space, but was not tested diachronically.

This qualitative review illustrates how models evolve towards increasing complexity to meet application demands, with validation following the developments of new model versions (Fig. S1). However, it also reveals the diversity within what we referred here as independent diachronic validation, including leave-one-site-out cross-validation approach, validation against reconstructed heterotrophic respiration dataset, against remaining C stocks following decomposition experiment, against C content, and against C stocks (Boxes S1&S2). Besides, some models aiming at prediction underwent only a partial independent validation³⁷, i.e., using sites partly overlapping those used for calibration (Box S1), some only consisted of model calibration and inter-comparisons⁴⁸, while others were only evaluated against static spatial data without evaluating the ability to reproduce temporal dynamics⁴⁷.

a MIMICS

	Non-diachronic evaluation	Diachronic evaluation
independent evaluation	Ability to predict spatial variability MIMICS (2020)	Ability to predict spatio-temporal dynamics MIMICS C-N (2015) MIMICS (2015) MIMICS (2014)
Non independent evaluation	Conceptualization	Calibration

b MILLENNIAL

	Non-diachronic evaluation	Diachronic evaluation
independent evaluation	Ability to predict spatial variability Millennial v2 (2022)	Ability to predict spatio-temporal dynamics
Non independent evaluation	Conceptualization Millennial v1 (2018)	Calibration

Fig. S5. Schematic representation of the (a) MIMICS and, (b) Millennial models and their validation pathways. Rectangles stand for processes, arrows stand for carbon fluxes, round stand for C pools.

Supplementary Notes 3:

Table S1. Summary of the systematic review of SOC models, the full database with all details is provided as Supplementary data (SI 2).

The numbers in the table read as follows:

Level: 1 = Microbial community model, 2 = Soil model, 3 = Ecosystem model, 4 = Global level

DEC: L = Linear (first-order) kinetic model, NL = Non-Linear kinetic model

Scope: (see scope definition in method section): 1 = Model aiming only to hypothesis-testing, 2 = Model aiming only to diagnosis, 3 = Model aiming only to prediction, 4 = Model aiming to 1, 2 and 3, 5 = Model with multiple objective including prediction (combination of scopes 1 and 3 and 2 and 3), 6 = Model with multiple objective excluding prediction (combination of scopes 1 and 2)

Types of Validation: 1 = No validation, 2 = Independent diachronic validation, 3 = Independent no diachronic validation (based on space for time or one point in time analysis), 4 = Diachronic non-independent validation, 5 = Non-independent no diachronic validation (based on space for time or one point in time analysis), 6 = Other type of validation (e.g., qualitative or average of several simulations against several observations)

Data used for Validation: 1 = Only against laboratory experiment, 2 = Only against field experiment, 3 = Only against SOC network measurement, 4 = Only against reconstructed datasets, 5 = Against both laboratory and field experiment, 6 = Against both laboratory experiment and SOC network measurement, 7 = Against both laboratory experiment and reconstructed dataset, 8 = Against both field experiment and SOC network measurements, 9 = Against both field experiment and reconstructed datasets, 10 = Against both network SOC measurement and reconstructed datasets, 11 = Against laboratory & field experiment and SOC network measurements, 12 = Against laboratory & field experiment and reconstructed datasets, 13 = Against laboratory experiment, SOC network measurements and reconstructed datasets, 14 = Against field experiment, SOC network measurements and reconstructed datasets, 15 = Against laboratory & laboratory experiments, SOC network measurements and reconstructed datasets, 16 = No Validation

Model	Ref.	Level	DEC	Scope	Types of Evaluation	Data used for Evaluation
No Name	⁴⁹	2	L	5	4	2
No Name	⁵⁰	2	L	2	1	0
No Name	⁵¹	2	L	5	3	2
No Name	⁵²	4	NL	1	1	0
No Name	⁵³	4	L	2	1	0
No Name	⁵⁴	2	L	1	1	0
PWNEE	⁵⁵	3	L	1	1	0
ABISKO	⁵⁶	3	L	1	1	0
ABISKO II	⁵⁷	3	L	5	4	2
No Name	⁵⁸	4	NL	1	1	0
No Name	⁵⁹	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	⁶⁰	3	L	3	4	2
No Name	⁶¹	1	NL	6	1	0
ELM	⁶²	3	L	5	2	2
Rothamsted	⁶³	2	L	5	2	2
No Name	⁶⁴	4	L	1	1	0

No Name	⁶⁵	2	L	2	5	0
No Name	⁶⁶	3	NL	1	1	0
No Name	⁶⁷	4	L	1	1	0
No Name	³⁵	2	L	6	4	1
No Name	⁶⁸	4	L	1	1	0
PHOENIX	⁶⁹	3	NL	5	3	2
PAPRAN	⁷⁰	3	NL	5	6	2
No Name	⁷¹	4	L	1	1	0
No Name	⁷²	2	L	1	4	1
No Name	⁷²	2	L	1	1	0
No Name	⁷³	2	NL	1	4	1
NCSOIL	⁷⁴	2	L	5	4	1
No Name	⁷⁵	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	⁷⁶	2	L	1	4	1
Q-Model	³⁶	2	L	4	6	1
No Name	⁷⁷	1	NL	1	1	0
JABOWA	⁷⁸	3	L	4	6	2
No Name	⁷⁹	2	NL	1	6	1
No Name	⁸⁰	2	L	3	3	2
CENTURY	²¹	2	L	3	3	5
Hurley	⁸¹	3	NL	1	1	0
Rothamsted	⁸²	2	L	3	4	2
Verberne	⁸³	2	L	5	5	4
MBL-GEM	⁸⁴	3	L	5	4	2
DNDC	⁸⁵	2	L	3	3	2
SUNDIAL	⁸⁶	2	L	3	5	2
G'DAY	⁸⁷	3	L	3	1	0
No Name	⁸⁸	2	NL	5	5	0
ecosys	⁸⁹	2	NL	5	4	1
FBM	⁹⁰	4	L	5	4	4
CENTURY (v2)	²³	3	L	5	5	2
CASA	⁹¹	4	L	1	4	8
No Name	⁹²	3	L	1	5	2
Q-Model	⁹³	2	L	1	3	7
No Name	⁹⁴	2	NL	1	2	1
No Name	⁹⁵	2	L	1	3	2
DEMETER	⁹⁶	4	L	3	3	10
No Name	⁹⁷	3	L	6	1	0
No Name	⁹⁸	3	L	1	4	2
Q-Model	⁹³	2	L	1	5	2
SCM	⁹⁹	2	NL	1	4	1
No Name	¹⁰⁰	2	L	6	1	0

8SV	101	3	L	6	1	0
No Name	102	2	NL	6	4	1
No Name	103	2	L	1	4	1
ICBM	104	2	L	5	4	2
SOMM	105	2	L	5	2	6
DocMod	106	2	L	2	3	3
Hybrid	107	4	L	5	1	0
No Name	108	2	L	6	4	1
No Name	109	3	L	6	3	0
No Name	110	2	NL	6	2	1
No Name	111	2	L	6	1	0
No Name	111	2	NL	6	1	0
NICA	112	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	113	2	NL	1	4	1
NCSOIL	114	2	NL	1	4	1
No Name	115	2	L	1	4	1
TCS	116	3	L	1	1	0
No Name	117	3	L	1	1	0
No Name	117	3	NL	1	1	0
IBIS	118	4	L	5	3	3
No Name	11	3	L	1	1	0
DAYCENT	119	3	L	3	6	2
PDM	120	2	NL	1	6	2
SOMKO	121	2	NL	5	2	2
Ecosys	122	3	NL	5	2	2
ICBM/N	123	2	L	5	5	2
ICBM/2BN	123	2	L	5	4	1
No Name	124	3	L	1	6	1
No Name	124	3	NL	1	6	1
G'DAY	125	3	L	1	1	0
TerraFlux	126	3	L	1	1	0
No Name	127	2	L	5	2	1
CREEP	128	3	L	5	3	2
No Name	9	2	L	1	1	0
CenW	129	3	L	3	6	8
No Name	130	3	L	6	4	2
TRACE	131	3	L	6	5	2
DyDOC	132	2	L	6	4	2
TAO	133	2	L	5	6	1
No Name	134	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	135	2	L	6	1	0
No Name	136	2	NL	1	1	0
LPJ	137	4	L	3	2	9

No Name	138	2	L	5	1	0
No Name	139	2	L	1	6	2
No Name	12	3	NL	1	1	0
MOMOS-2	140	2	L	3	2	2
EnzModel	141	1	NL	1	1	0
No Name	142	3	NL	1	1	0
INDISIM-SOM	143	1	NL	6	4	1
Yasso	144	2	L	3	3	2
IBIS	145	4	L	5	6	4
No Name	146	1	NL	1	1	0
CN-SIM	147	2	L	3	2	2
CN-SIM	148	2	L	3	2	1
No Name	149	2	NL	5	1	0
BACWAVE-WEB	150	2	NL	5	2	1
No Name	151	1	NL	5	1	0
CIPS	152	2	L	3	2	2
No Name	153	2	L	1	6	1
No Name	154	2	L	1	2	1
MIOR	155	2	NL	1	1	0
MOMOS-6	8	2	L	1	4	1
No Name	10	2	L	6	2	2
No Name	10	2	NL	6	2	2
No Name	156	3	L	5	6	2
SPACSYS	157	3	L	5	6	5
No Name	158	2	L	1	1	0
Roth PC-1	159	2	L	3	4	2
No Name	160	2	L	6	6	0
AMGv1	32	2	L	5	2	2
No Name	161	3	L	1	1	0
Struc-C	162	2	L	1	1	0
No Name	163	2	NL	5	5	2
MOMOS-6	164	3	L	3	4	2
No Name	165	2	NL	1	4	1
ICBM	166	1	L	3	4	2
Not named	167	2	NL	1	1	0
Not named	168	2	L	5	4	1
Not Name	169	2	L	5	4	2
SOMPROF	170	3	L	5	3	2
Not named	171	3	L	5	2	2
SOIL-CO2/RothC	172	2	NL	1	1	0

DEMENT	173	2	L	3	4	2
Herbert Model	174	2	NL	1	1	0
Not named	175	2	NL	1	1	0
EEZY	176	2	NL	1	1	0
Pirt Model	176	2	NL	1	1	0
ICBM with erosion added	177	2	L	5	4	2
No Name	178	3	L	1	1	0
SOMPROF	179	3	L	5	5	2
CAST	180	3	L	1	6	2
MIN1-TA	181	2	L	4	4	2
ICBM - AssimEplcicit	182	2	NL	1	1	0
CLM4cn	183	4	L	5	3	14
CLM microbial model	183	4	NL	4	3	14
Roth-C	184	2	L	5	2	2
MEND	185	2	NL	1	1	0
CLM-CN	186	4	L	5	3	10
Not named	187	2	L	1	4	1
AggModel	188	2	L	1	3	1
Not named	189	2	NL	1	1	0
Not named	190	2	NL	5	5	2
Revised GDM	191	2	NL	4	4	1
DEMENT	192	2	NL	1	1	0
EnzMax	193	3	NL	5	6	8
I14CBM	194	3	L	3	4	5
CANTIS	195	2	L	3	4	1
SYMPHONY	196	1	NL	1	1	0
BAMS1	197	4	NL	3	3	8
SCAMPS	198	3	NL	1	1	0
DAMM	199	2	NL	1	1	0
MOSAIC	200	2	L	1	4	1
CORPSE	201	2	NL	6	4	5
C-TOOL	202	2	L	1	4	2
CMIP-5	203	4	L	5	5	4
Daycent	39	2	L	2	3	4
MEND	204	2	NL	1	4	1
Wieder model (2013)	204	2	NL	1	6	5
German model (2012)	204	2	NL	1	6	5
MIMICS	39	2	NL	1	2	2

No Name	205	2	NL	1	1	0
4C_NOSM	206	2	NL	1	2	2
COMISSION	207	2	NL	6	5	2
No Name	208	2	L	1	2	2
No Name	209	1	NL	1	1	0
LBios	210	2	NL	1	1	0
MEND	211	2	NL	1	4	1
MIMICS	40	2	NL	5	2	9
LIDEL	212	2	L	6	2	1
RothCE	213	2	L	6	2	9
1-group model (producer)	214	1	NL	1	1	0
PRIM	29	5	L	3	2	1
ORCHIDEE- PRIM	29	5	L	3	2	2
ICBM	215	2	L	1	4	2
FWD	216	2	NL	1	1	0
FOD	216	2	L	1	1	0
No name	13	1	NL	6	4	1
DAMM- MCNiP	217	2	NL	6	4	2
CAMP	218	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	219	3	NL	1	5	2
No Name	220	2	NL	1	3	2
ROTHC	221	2	L	3	4	1
SEAM	222	3	NL	1	4	2
BAMS1	223	2	NL	1	5	2
Millennial	46	2	NL	1	1	0
SMMARTS	224	2	NL	1	1	0
ORCHIDEE- SOM	225	3	L	6	4	2
CARBOSAF	226	2	L	1	5	2
No Name	227	2	L	1	4	2
Soilgen2.15	228	2	L	1	5	2
ORCHIDEE- PRIM	30	3	L	5	2	7
ORCHIDEE- MICT	229	3	L	1	1	0
Ib-LBioS- Comp	230	1	NL	1	1	0
ORCHIMIC	231	2	NL	1	4	1
Century	43	2	L	5	5	4
CLM4.5bgc	43	3	L	5	5	4

MIMICS	⁴³	2	NL	5	5	4
DAMM-FoBAAR	²³²	3	NL	1	4	2
DAYCENT	⁴⁴	2	L	6	2	2
MIMICS	⁴⁴	2	NL	6	3	2
CORPSE	⁴⁴	2	NL	6	2	2
ORCHIDEE-SOM	²³³	3	L	6	3	2
CENTURY-CUE	²³⁴	2	L	1	2	1
CASA-CNP	¹⁹	4	L	4	3	4
MIMICS	¹⁹	4	NL	4	3	4
Q model	²³⁵	2	L	1	1	0
IndiMeSH	²³⁶	1	NL	5	6	1
AMGv2	¹⁴	2	L	5	2	2
T&C-BG	²³⁷	3	NL	1	2	2
CANDY CCB	²³⁸	2	L	6	4	2
No name	²³⁹	2	L	1	4	1
OC-VGEN	²⁴⁰	3	L	1	2	2
Michaelis Menten and Monod kinetics Biomass-based competition	²⁴¹	1	NL	1	4	1
Michaelis Menten and Monod kinetics Biomass-based inhibition	²⁴¹	1	NL	1	4	1
First-order kinetic model	²⁴²	2	L	5	4	1
Dormancy kinetics model	²⁴²	2	NL	5	4	1
Yasso	²⁴³	2	L	3	2	3
Q model	²⁴⁴	2	L	5	4	2
MEMS	²⁴⁵	3	L	1	3	3
Qualitative model (No name)	²⁴⁶	2	L	3	6	2
ENSEMBLE modelling including three biogeochemical	⁴⁵	4	L	5	1	0

models: CASA-CNP, MIMICS ad CORPSE						
SOMic 1.0.	²⁴⁷	5	NL	1	2	9
ENSEMBLE modelling including four biogeochemical models: 1 first order kinetic model and 3 microbial- explicit models	²⁴⁸	2	L	1	6	1
No name	²⁴⁹	1	NL	1	1	0
SMMARTS	²⁵⁰	2	NL	1	4	1
Linear	²⁵¹	1	L	1	1	0
Multiplicative	²⁵¹	1	NL	1	1	0
Keylinks	²⁵²	2	NL	5	6	2
N14CP-Agri	²⁵³	3	L	5	2	2
CASA-CNP	⁴²	4	L	3	2	9
MIMICS	⁴²	4	NL	3	2	4
CORPSE	⁴²	4	NL	3	2	4
MEND	⁴²	2	NL	6	2	5
MIMICS C-N	⁴¹	5	NL	3	4	5
MIMICS C-N	⁴¹	5	NL	3	3	5
DAISY	²⁵⁴	2	L	3	2	2
AMGv2	²⁵⁵	2	L	5	4	2
AMGv3	⁴⁸	2	L	5	4	2
No name	²⁵⁶	2	L	3	2	2
No Name	²⁵⁷	2	L	5	3	5
Yasso 5	²⁵⁸	3	L	3	4	2
PROMISE (Probabilistic Representation of Organic Matter Interactions within the Soil Environment)	²⁵⁹	2	NL	1	1	0
Jena Soil Model	²⁶⁰	2	NL	1	5	2
CENTURY	²⁶¹	5	L	3	5	2

MIMICS-def	²⁶¹	5	NL	3	5	2
Millennial	⁴⁷	2	NL	1	3	0
No Name	²⁶²	2	NL	4	2	1
MIMICS simplification	²⁶³	2	NL	6	6	2
MIND Michaelis–Menten necromass decomposition model	²⁶⁴	2	L	1	2	5
FOND First-Order Necromass Decomposition model	²⁶⁴	2	NL	1	4	5
ORCHIMIC 2.0	¹⁵	2	NL	3	3	4
Daisy	²⁶⁵	2	L	6	4	5
No Name	²⁶⁶	2	L	1	1	0
C-STABILITY scenario 1,2 & 4	³⁸	2	NL	1	1	0
No Name	²⁶⁷	3	L	5	3	9
MIMICS-DBT	²⁶⁸	5	NL	1	3	2
MEMS 2.0	²⁶⁹	3	L	1	3	2

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